

TDCC-LSH

Life Sciences & Health

Thematic Digital Competence Centre for Life Sciences and Health

***TDCC-LSH Self-evaluation report
September 2022- August 2025***

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Authors:

- Celia van Gelder (Health-RI), Network Manager TDCC-LSH
- Kimberley Zwiers (Health-RI), Community Coordinator Life Sciences TDCC-LSH
- Fieke Schoots (Health-RI), Community Coordinator Health TDCC-LSH
- Ruben Kok (Health-RI), Chair Programme Board TDCC-LSH

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Contact information TDCC-LSH

- € TDCC website: <https://tdcc.nl/>
- € Email: lsh@tdcc.nl

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Executive Summary

The Thematic Digital Competence Centre for Life Sciences & Health (TDCC-LSH) was launched in 2022 with support from the Dutch Research Council (NWO), as one of three national TDCCs to strengthen digitalisation of research, and specifically to enhance competencies across organisations in the Dutch academic field. The TDCC-LSH mission is to advance data-driven health and life sciences by harmonising data stewardship, improving interoperability of digital solutions, and developing the skills of researchers and data professionals.

TDCC-LSH Progress 2022–2025

In three years' time, TDCC-LSH has developed into a recognised and trusted national platform enabling knowledge exchange and collaboration. Firstly, TDCC-LSH has built up a solid network by (co-)organising and attending more than 70 community events, and by establishing working relationships with major LSH stakeholders, initially most prominently the LSRI (incl Health-RI), BioSB and ELIXIR-NL. To keep connected to the more discipline-agnostic needs, challenges and solutions, close collaboration is in place with TDCC-NES, TDCC-SSH and the LDCCs at universities, UMCs and other research performing organisations, as well as with LCRDM, SURF and eScienceCenter. The Data Steward Interest Group (DSIG), home base of the Dutch data stewards, is growing to involve data stewards across research domains and is now supported by the three TDCCs together. Secondly, a strong project portfolio involving a broad range of stakeholders has been built up to address bottlenecks in data driven research in the life sciences and health field and develop sustainable, community-driven solutions. Two project calls have been run under the governance of the TDCC-LSH Programme Board and seven community-led projects have been launched in 2025, focusing on FAIR data stewardship, interoperability of workflows, metadata, harmonisation of common data elements, training and capacity building. Demand for funding in the two project calls was more than four times higher than available resources, underlining the urgency and relevance of the programme. In recent consultations, stakeholders indicate that the value of TDCC-LSH is its convening power, its role in supporting projects that otherwise would not be funded, and its contribution to training & capacity building, harmonization, standards and community building. Key priorities remain sustainability of outcomes, stronger communication, and transparency in project selection. Despite operating with a small team and limited budget, the programme has efficiently delivered a broad range of network activities and a strategic project portfolio.

Strategic Outlook

A SWOT analysis highlights TDCC-LSH's strengths in community trust, national reach, and policy influence, while capacity and funding remain major constraints. Weaknesses relate to the current small size of the TDCC-LSH relatively to the size of the field it serves. Perceived risks relate to sustainability, long project lead times and the currently fragmented national coordination. Opportunities to secure further strengthening of the TDCC-LSH programme and its sustained positioning include alignment with several emerging initiatives in the national (research) data landscape, in sync with European Data Spaces and research infrastructure initiatives. TDCC-LSH is also well positioned in Open Science NL. Future funding opportunities are explored via the upcoming LSRI Roadmap connecting to the European infrastructures in the LSH field.

Conclusion

TDCC-LSH has established itself as a unique and indispensable instrument in the Dutch research data landscape. To secure long-term impact, structural funding and clearer national coordination are essential to sustain its role as a catalyst for collaboration, capacity building, and interoperable digital solutions in life sciences and health.

Chapter 1 – TDCC-LSH: Background and strategy

1.1 Background: roadmap, ambitions and embedding

Since Autumn 2022, three national-level Thematic Digital Competence Centres (TDCC) have been established in the Netherlands for the scientific domains Life Sciences & Health (TDCC-LSH), Natural & Engineering Sciences (TDCC-NES) and Social Sciences & Humanities (TDCC-SSH). The role of the TDCCs is to help tackle domain specific challenges in data driven science by a combination of network activities and dedicated project funding.

The TDCCs all build on the national e-infrastructure already established in the Netherlands (SURF in collaboration with the academic organisations) and are complementary to the Local Digital Competence Centers (LDCC) at institute level, offering support to scientists and data stewards within their organisation. LDCCs and TDCCs are all supported by NWO as part of the [Dutch Implementation Plan Investments Digital Research Infrastructure \(2019\)](#). Per invitation by NWO, three teams were appointed in 2021 as quartermasters to prepare for each TDCC by consulting stakeholders in their respective science fields and formulate a [roadmap, to guide the TDCC activities](#), within the constraints put forward by NWO (funding level, community involvement, synergy in the field).

- **FAIR Implementation** – Practical approaches to making data and software findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable
- **Software & Tools** – Finding the right tool for the right job and sustainability of software
- **ICT: computing & storage** – Operating secure processing environments for analysis of privacy-sensitive and otherwise sensitive data
- **Human capital** – Training & capacity building of digital experts
- **Support from research funders** – Improve conditions for good data stewardship and rewards & recognition for FAIR implementation
- **Communication** – Sharing of success stories, e.g. about the benefits of FAIR data, and community building

Figure 1: Themes with common challenges among stakeholders in the data-driven health and life sciences field, as identified in the stakeholder consultation phase in 2021 that led to the TDCC-LSH Roadmap in 2022.

The TDCC-LSH Roadmap translated the key challenges widely experienced in the field to prioritised topics to address in the TDCC-LSH programme (Figure 1). It also showed how the TDCC-LSH role could build on the expertise, overview and network of Health-RI and the Dutch Techcentre for Life sciences (DTL), merged with Health-RI in 2023). The TDCC-LSH Roadmap has been approved by NWO in 2022, after a positive advice from the [Permanent Committee for large-scale scientific infrastructure \(PC-GWI\)](#).

The overarching goal of TDCC-LSH is to advance the field of data driven health and life research by helping to strengthen the digital competencies and digital practices across stakeholders in the broad Dutch research domains of life sciences and biomedical/health sciences.

The three ambitions of TDCC-LSH have been formulated as follows:

1. **Harmonisation of good data stewardship and data access practices;**
2. **Enhancement of the interoperability of digital solutions and resources; and**
3. **Strengthening the capacity and expertise base in digital research.**

1.2 Role and strategy: common platform connecting initiatives

The TDCC-LSH positions itself as a common national stakeholder 'platform'. Its primary role, through its network activities and projects, is to bring researchers and data professionals together to agree on steps forward in data-driven health and life sciences and subsequently help realise collaborative projects. As such, the programme is much more than a dedicated NWO funding stream. To make this role work, the TDCC-LSH Programme Board adopted the strategy to involve key national stakeholders that already have a national role in the LSH domain, can oversee international developments and, where possible, have the expertise and capacity to bundle efforts to help realise the common TDCC-LSH agenda.

Important national LSH initiatives to start with were the [national large-scale scientific infrastructures \(LSRI\) co-funded in the framework of the Dutch infrastructure Roadmap](#), next to [Health-RI](#) designing the Dutch national health data infrastructure for research. Together, these initiatives offer advanced (experimental) infrastructures and related data management processes across the LSH domain, safeguarding the best quality data. Collectively, they oversee the advancements and (international) standards and solutions to best analyse specific data types (e.g. ~omics, bioimaging) in the framework of the research questions of broader LSH research fields (e.g. health, green life sciences).

Also, the position of [ELIXIR-NL](#) as part of the cross-connecting European infrastructure for health & life sciences data, and [BioSB](#), convening the bioinformatics and computational biology community in the Netherlands, were important communities to involve in the TDCC-LSH programme. Through the [Data Stewards Interest Group \(DSIG\)](#) already set up in DTL in 2017, TDCC-LSH actively involves the community of domain-specific data stewards in a more bottom-up fashion. The DSIG is growing to involve data stewards across science domains and is now supported by the three TDCCs together.

Furthermore, TDCC LSH represents the LSH community in [Research Data Netherlands \(RDNL\)](#), a consortium of four partners including Health-RI. RDNL is since long committed to support the implementation of FAIR data. With funding from [Open Science NL \(OSNL\)](#), RDNL is currently working closely with all stakeholders to build a [national training and community platform](#). This platform will meet the need for qualified research data professionals in the transition to Open Science through a harmonised curriculum based on job profiles in Dutch RPO's.

Through its positioning in Health-RI, TDCC-LSH is very well connected to European developments relevant for the data-driven LSH domain: 1] European data spaces, in particular the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), plus 2] national nodes in [European research infrastructures in the life and medical sciences \(LMS-RIs\) that are building a common strategy](#).

We also work closely together with TDCC-NES, TDCC-SSH and the LDCCs in UMCs and Universities, to keep connected to the more discipline-overarching needs, challenges and solutions. For generic e-infrastructure-related solutions and generic services, SURF is involved in both network activities and projects. Discussions have been held with The Netherlands eScience Centre, which also led to proposed involvement in projects, but their involvement has been temporarily halted in view of a recent reorganisation.

Along with the other DCCs, the TDCC-LSH is also well positioned in the framework of the transition to Open Science, and regarded as a national stakeholder by Open Science NL. In preparing to connect the Dutch field to the EOSC, the TDCC-LSH helps shape the model of a Dutch national node in the EOSC Federation. This confirms the strategic value of the TDCCs as national programme. To ensure effective stakeholder engagement, key groups of TDCC-LSH stakeholders have been identified, see Figure 2 below, as described in the [TDCC-LSH KPI document](#).

Figure 2: Overview of identified stakeholders in the TDCC-LSH landscape.

1.3 Organisation & Governance

The TDCC-LSH programme is coordinated by Health-RI, home to the TDCC-LSH coordination team (2 fte for a first period of 5 years). Per directive of NWO, a TDCC-LSH Programme Board has been installed to oversee the TDCC-LSH activities that comprise of both network activities and building a growing TDCC-LSH project portfolio (described further below). The Programme Board has a crucial role to prioritise community-based project proposals that are led to NWO for (co-)funding.

The **TDCC-LSH Programme Board (PB)** is in place since November 2023, and is composed of members that represent major communities in the broad data driven Health and Life Sciences research domain. These include a representative from each of the four groups of the Roadmap Large Scale Research infrastructures (LSRI), representatives from key national initiatives in the Life Sciences and Health domain, and NWO and ZonMw as observers. This secures that there is a good overview over the full LSH field and its data challenges.

The **TDCC-LSH Coordination Team** is a small team positioned at host organization Health-RI and consists of a network manager, two community coordinators (for Health and Life Sciences), a FAIR data stewardship Lead and since Summer 2025 two interoperability experts (funded by Open Science NL). The team informs all relevant stakeholders in the TDCC-LSH network and coordinates the TDCC-LSH programme. The TDCC-LSH coordination team also facilitates the community-driven project call process and supports the Programme Board in guiding or monitoring the progress of TDCC-LSH.

Detailed information about the TDCC-LSH Governance can be found in Appendix 5 and also on the [TDCC-LSH website](#).

Chapter 2 – Progress along KPIs and financial realisation

2.1 TDCC-LSH KPIs

Per request of NWO, TDCC-LSH has formulated its [KPIs](#) (January 2023) and identified its most relevant stakeholder groups (see above). The formulated three KPIs for an active TDCC-LSH network were defined in qualitative and quantitative terms:

KPI 1: TDCC-LSH Network activities (WHAT)

KPI 2: Engagement in/involvement of the stakeholders in TDCC-LSH activities (WITH WHOM)

KPI 3: Progress perceived by the TDCC-LSH stakeholders (OUTCOMES)

The committee DO has approved the TDCC-LSH KPIs and indicated they would be used for the evaluation. In the following sections the progress of TDCC-LSH will be reported according to these KPIs. Table 1 shows the relation between the ToR criteria and the TDCC-LSH KPIs, as well as the respective sections in this report where these are discussed.

Table 1: mapping of the TDCC-LSH KPIs with the criteria in the Terms of Reference (ToR)

Evaluation Criterium	KPI TDCC-LSH	Section of this report
Quality , with elements network building and knowledge transfer	KPI1, KPI2, KPI3	Chapter 1 (TDCC-LSH Roadmap), Chapter 2 (network activities and project portfolio) and Appendix 2 and 3 (network activities and project portfolio)
Relevance , with elements demand of the TDCC domain and Impact on the TDCC domain	KPI2, KPI3	Chapter 1 (alignment with TDCC-LSH Roadmap), Chapter 2 (activities, & stakeholder consultations)
Viability , with elements sustainability, organisational robustness, strategic flexibility, governance, position in the domain of operation and proportionality of resources	KPI3	Chapter 2 (establishment of close working relations with stakeholders), Chapter 3 (SWOT and strategic outlook), and Appendix 3 (Finances)

2.2 TDCC-LSH activities & stakeholder engagement (KPI1&KPI2)

The TDCC-LSH activities can be divided in two main parts, which are separately funded by NWO:

- Network activities, organized by the TDCC-LSH core team at Health-RI
- The TDCC-LSH project portfolio, funded through separate dedicated NWO calls

Table 2 gives an aggregated overview of selected TDCC-LSH activities in the period September 2022 – September 2025 (details further below and in Appendices 1 and 2)

Table 2: Aggregated overview of selected TDCC-LSH activities September 2022-September 2025

Network activities	Number	Comment
Events (co-)organized	33	
Events attended (outreach)	38	
Data Steward Interest Group meetings (cross-domain)	12 meetings	Collaboratively with TDCC-SSH and TDCC-NES

Project related activities

<i>Eol submitted in challenge project calls</i>	32	2023-2025, two independent calls
<i>TDCC-LSH projects</i>	9	

2.2.1 Network activities

In the three years of its existence TDCC-LSH has established strong working relationships with all major LSH stakeholders, whom we brought together in workshops and one-on-one meetings to discuss joint data-related challenges and solutions, share knowledge and expertise, align on methodologies and best practices and kickstart collaborations between initiatives. Altogether, we have (co-)organized 33 community workshops and events and in addition we attended 38 events organised by stakeholders in the field in various topics, to present ongoing work and raise awareness about the role and activities of TDCC-LSH. Appendix 1 shows an overview of all the network activities undertaken for and with the TDCC-LSH stakeholders in the period September 2022- September 2025. In addition to the co-organized and attended events and meetings shown we have had numerous specific one-on-one meetings and discussions with specific stakeholders (e.g. challenge call applicants, LSRIs, LDCCs). These are not included in the numbers in the table.

Examples of (co-)organised and attended events are the [Teaming up across domains](#) event in February 2024 (together with the other TDCCs and the National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM), the [Data Stewards job profiles workshop](#) in 2023, a session related to the [TDCC-LSH project portfolio at the BioSB Annual conference 2025, meetings with Large Scale Research Infrastructures \(LSRIs\) in the LSH domain](#) (Dutch: GWIs), NWO life 2023 and 2024, the German CORDI/NFDI conference 2025, the [ELIXIR Europe All Hands meeting 2025](#) and the [EOOSC NL Tripartite event](#) (2023 and 2024). More details about specific events in the period 2022-2024 can also be found in Appendix 2B of the [2022-2024 year report of TDCC-LSH](#).

Data Steward Interest Group (DSIG)

One of the key network activities we have actively further developed in TDCC-LSH is the Data Steward Interest Group (DSIG), bringing together experts in data stewardship roles across the field in regular online topical meetings. While originally set up in the life sciences domain, as TDCCs together we extended its scope to cover a broad range of topics related to data stewardship, across domains. The DSIG mailing list has 384 members and the slack space has 190 active members (mostly from the Netherlands, but also from abroad). With the monthly series '[Spotlight on data stewards](#)', which features 14 LSH data stewards (out of a total of 48 portraits), we are helping to increase the visibility of data stewards within their organisations and the research community in general.

Communication channels

NWO asked for a collective website for the TDCCs (<https://tdcc.nl/>) which is used to communicate about network activities and projects. The website has sections for news items and blogs, both collectively and for each TDCC separately. To reach out to the community, TDCC LSH consciously uses communication channels that already exist and are familiar to the community: mailing lists of the [National Coordination Point RDM](#) (LCRDM), [DSIG](#) and [DCC-Implementation Network](#) (DCC-IN), as well as the active [DSIG slack channel](#) and [Health-RI's](#) LinkedIn account. The [TDCC-LSH Zenodo community](#) contains key publications of TDCC-LSH. An extensive report of the activities of the first two years of TDCC-LSH was published in December 2024 ([Strengthening the Dutch data driven health & life sciences field - TDCC-LSH facts and figures September 2022 - August 2024](#)).

2.2.2 Project portfolio

The project portfolio supported by TDCC-LSH aims to strengthen the Life Sciences and Health domain by advancing collaborative, high-quality and sustainable research data practices and is shown in Table 3. With a collective start of the first batch of projects early 2025, funded from several separate calls through NWO, the TDCC-LSH programme has entered a new phase. At the moment of writing, 8 projects are ongoing (the network coordination project (P1) with startdate September 2022 and 7 projects with starting dates between April 1 and September 1, 2025 (P2-P8)), and 1 project (P9) will start soon. The project portfolio and more detailed descriptions of each project are available on the [TDCC-LSH website](#) and in Appendix 2D, including summaries and an overview of participating partner institutions.

Table 3: TDCC-LSH project portfolio September 2025. (*) indicate projects that have been selected by the TDCC-LSH projects call 2023/2024, as described in section 2.2.3 and Appendix 2.

Project code	Project Title	Start Date	Duration (months)	Total budget
P1 (Network)	Thematic Digital Competence Center - Coordination of the Life Sciences & Health (TDCC-LSH) network	1 Sept 2022	60	1420 k€ (NWO) + 270 k€ (in-kind) + 50k€ other costs
P2 (Fellowship)	Strengthening the Dutch LSH FAIR data stewardship landscape – installing a national cohort of FAIR LSH fellows	1 Apr 2025	18	€ 877.776,00
P3 (Toolbox)	A FAIR tool framework for bioinformatics services, tools and workflows in digital Life Sciences and Health (LSH) research	1 Apr 2025	24	€ 394.325,00 (*)
P4 (LEARN-FAIR)	LEARN-FAIR: Life Science & Health Educational Alignment for Research and Networking in FAIR Data Management	1 Apr 2025	24	€ 399.857,00 (*)
P5 (FAIR-aware)	Training the next generation of FAIR-aware and AI-savvy data scientists for the LSH domain	1 Jun 2025	24	€ 243.158,00 (*)
P6 (Interoperability-OSNL)	Collective research data workflow assembly to enhance FAIR practices across the Dutch Life Sciences and Health domain	1 Jun 2025	44	€ 998.128,00
P7 (FAIRify)	FAIRify your metabolomicsdata: achieving convergence on standards for reuse-ready data and workflows (FAIRify)	1 Aug 2025	24	€ 329.930,00 (*)
P8 (Cohorts)	Prospective harmonization of variables through Common Data Elements – towards a core cohort dataset for cohort studies in the Netherlands	1 Sep 2025	24	€ 231.760,00 (*)
P9 (LSRI)	Towards Practical FAIR Metadata Use in Life Science Research Infrastructures	T.B.D.	12	€ 70.651,00

Looking at TDCC-LSH's project portfolio, it is clear that the projects are addressing the challenges identified in the TDCC-LSH Roadmap. Core priorities being tackled in the projects include building LSH data stewardship expertise and establishing national networks of experts to drive the adoption and implementation of FAIR data principles in the LSH domain. Key challenges addressed include metadata management, interoperability and standardization of common data elements to enable data sharing across studies, institutions and large-scale research infrastructures. The portfolio places emphasis on FAIR-by-design workflows, prospective harmonisation strategies and the integration of software and tools to support robust, scalable and sustainable research data management. Education and capacity building are equally important, with efforts directed at developing FAIR data stewardship training,

creating open educational resources and embedding data stewardship practices across research life sciences and health communities. Additionally, the portfolio addresses cross-cutting themes such as artificial intelligence, bioinformatics and metabolomics by advancing semantic standards and interoperable data frameworks. Ultimately, the portfolio aims to foster collaboration, develop scalable solutions and build communities of practice that enable reproducible and interoperable science.

2.2.3 Project selection process

Organization of the project selection process

In close alignment with NWO, significant efforts have been dedicated to developing and implementing the selection process for the TDCC-LSH Challenge Projects, as well as facilitating project teams and potential applicants in preparing their proposals. The project development process has been highly successful to date. Having executed two iterations of its Challenge Project selection process in 2023–2024 and again one in 2025. The process is designed to guide applicants through a structured, collaborative and feedback-driven pathway that supports the development of high-quality, impactful and interdisciplinary research proposals that align with community priorities and national funding strategies in the life sciences and health domain. TDCC-LSH has demonstrated a strong commitment to foster community-driven and interdisciplinary collaboration. By continuously refining its approach in response to participant feedback and an evolving research landscape, TDCC-LSH has established a flexible and effective mechanism for identifying high-impact projects in the life sciences and health domain. A complete description of the TDCC-LSH Challenge call process can be found on the [TDCC-LSH website](#) or in Appendix 2A.

Distribution of partners across proposals

Between 2023-2025, more than 32 project ideas were submitted. A total funding budget of €10.1 million was requested, which was roughly five times more than the €2.4 million available. In the 2023–2024 process, €7.5 million was requested against an available budget of just €1.6 million. In 2025, €2.6 million was requested with only €0.8 million available. These figures clearly demonstrate that demand for funding significantly exceeds the resources available, highlighting the importance of a robust selection process that promotes strategic alignment and fosters stronger collaboration among applicants. The (co-)applicants were spread over all the institutes of the Netherlands and covered the full breadth of LSH. University Medical Centers (UMCs) showed the strongest engagement with over twice the average proposal involvement per institution compared to universities. A complete overview of all projects, including their project titles and associated collaborating institutions, can be found in Appendix 2B and 2C.

2.3 Progress perceived by the TDCC-LSH stakeholders (KPI3)

Summer 2025, a series of dedicated stakeholder consultations was set up in order to gain insight into the views of TDCC-LSH stakeholders on both the efforts of the first three years and the future. Progress perceived by the stakeholders specifically targeted a) TDCC-LSH network activities b) TDCC-LSH projects (both the application process as well as the portfolio of projects) and c) TDCC-LSH in general as instrument in the Dutch landscape. The list of stakeholder consultations is in Appendix 4. What follows is a summary of the feedback of the LSH stakeholders.

2.3.1 Stakeholder views on the network activities

The TDCC-LSH network activities are highly valued by stakeholders as they strengthen both personal and professional connections, fostering future collaborations and projects. It was noted that the network activities helped local and thematic DCC's to position themselves and to collaborate already in the initial phase. Community events, workshops, and the Data Steward Interest Group (DSIG) play a central role in connecting and informing the data stewardship community in the Netherlands.

Stakeholders highlight the need for clearer, streamlined communication channels (TDCCs, LCRDM, LDCC network, etc), and a shared overview of relevant news, events, policy, tools & resources, infrastructure, (inter)national developments in the field for all LSH stakeholders. Finally, improving visibility (e.g. via social media) and strengthening connections with related initiatives (such as LSRI) are seen as important next steps.

Stakeholder quotes

1. “The DSIG meeting is at the top of the list of events that should never go away—it’s essential for staying connected with the community” – *Kristina Hettne, Leiden University*
2. “Talking with TDCC-LSH means talking with the whole field” – *Peter Hinrich, SURF*
3. “Community engagement is essential for TDCC-LSH success. Strong networks don’t run themselves—active support and sustained involvement are key to making them thrive.” – *Patrick Kemmeren, Princess Maxima Center for Pediatric Oncology, Board member BioSB*
4. “Continue to collaborate between LSRI and TDCC and make it more fluent and focus on the services that we can exchange between each other: – *Geerten Hengeveld, NIOO-KNAW, LTER-LIFE.*

2.3.2 Stakeholder views on the project call process

The project call process received mixed feedback. Some stakeholders experienced it as tedious for the amount of funding involved, while others found it relatively lightweight and appropriate for the amount of funding involved. Several stakeholders emphasized the wish for greater transparency in the project selection and insight in the strategic vision of the TDCC-LSH Programme Board for building the TDCC-LSH portfolio. The lack of a process for cross-TDCC applications was also noted. Despite challenges such as thinly spread funding and difficulties in staff allocation, the calls have been valuable in fostering new collaborations. After the feedback of the stakeholders on the 2023/2024 process simplifications were introduced in the second year, which was widely appreciated and made the process more accessible.

Stakeholder quotes

- “The process was very useful – it really brought people together that did not work together before.” – *Magnus Palmblad, LUMC, Head of Node ELIXIR-NL*
- “A broad base with many institutes promotes collaboration, but it spreads the funding thin.” – *Peter-Bram 't Hoen, Radboudumc, X-omics*

2.3.3 Stakeholder views on the project portfolio

Stakeholders are overall very positive about the current TDCC-LSH project portfolio. They value its focus on training & capacity building, harmonization, standards and community building. The projects are appreciated as they address topics that would otherwise not receive funding and as bringing people and institutes together beyond research. At the same time, stakeholders stress the importance of ensuring sustainability and implementation of results within institutions, so that outcomes become embedded in daily practice. While the portfolio is considered strong, challenges remain in ensuring sufficient resources, reaching beyond data experts to researchers, and balancing institutional focus with national-level ambitions.

Stakeholder quotes

- “We need to make sure that these projects go on and results get implemented and become part of our way of working in the long run.” – *Efi Gkoumassi, UMCG LDCC*

- “The projects address important topics where you would not get funding in other calls.” – *Patrick Kemmeren, Princess Maxima Center for Pediatric Oncology, Board member BioSB*
- “I was skeptical about the financing of projects, but I now see that it is bringing the field forward... it is nice to see that it is not only about research – projects bring the community together.” – *Kristina Hettne, Leiden University*

2.3.4 Stakeholder views on the role of TDCC-LSH in the Dutch landscape

Interviewees record that TDCC-LSH plays a central role in connecting the Dutch life sciences community and address national-level data and infrastructure challenges in health and life sciences. They value the efforts in fostering collaboration, building communities, and providing guidance, which are unique compared to structures in other countries. While local DCCs sometimes lack capacity to fully engage with the TDCCs, TDCC-LSH helps coordinate and align efforts across institutions. The TDCC-activities are seen as closely aligned with the TDCC-LSH Roadmap, though funding and scale remain limited.

Many emphasize the need for clearer national coordination, clarifying role division between generic and domain-specific activities and partners, and stronger top-down support to amplify impact. TDCC-LSH is regarded as a trusted point of contact, a catalyst for progress, and a platform that connects Dutch life sciences to international initiatives. Overall, it provides momentum, visibility, and structure in a rapidly evolving data and research landscape.

Stakeholder quotes

1. "This is a unique instrument that does not exist in other countries. The Netherlands should significantly strengthen the TDCCs and make them a sustainable part of the European research data landscape" – *Karel Luyben, President Emeritus of the EOSC Association*
2. “As far as we are concerned, the TDCCs have laid a strong foundation. We see TDCC-LSH as the point of contact for the LSH field.” – *Laurents Sesink, SURF*
3. “There is a great need for training and helping people, and TDCC-LSH serves as a national platform connecting infrastructure development and international collaboration.” – *Magnus Palmblad, LUMC, ELIXIR-NL*
4. "As ZonMw we support the role of the TDCC-LSH programme and its network, and we are looking forward to learn from the outcomes, such as guidelines to implement FAIR, to improve our research calls." – *Ellen Carbo, ZonMw.*
5. “We are developing together in the good direction, as local and thematic DCC’s are complementary and working together on raising awareness, increasing the expertise of support professionals and implementing standards. In this we improve the Dutch research support landscape in close collaboration” – *Marcel Ras, VU LDCC, DCC-IN*

2.4 TDCC-LSH finances

This paragraph is intentionally left blank in the public version of the TDCC-LSH self-evaluation report.

Chapter 3 – TDCC-LSH: Current position and strategic outlook towards sustainability

In this chapter we take stock of where we stand, just over halfway the first phase of the TDCC-LSH. To assess the best way going forward to direct the TDCC-LSH programme, we have conducted an overall SWOT analysis with the TDCC-LSH Programme Board and coordination team. Based on these insights, combined with the input from stakeholders in line with KPI3 (*Progress perceived by the TDCC-LSH stakeholders*, see previous chapter), we have derived actionable steps forward to enhance the impact of the TDCC-LSH within the field of data-driven health and life sciences in the coming years. In addition, we are using this analysis to help build a strategy to sustainably embed TDCC-LSH as a common national platform in the Dutch research data landscape to secure long-term impact.

3.1 SWOT analysis TDCC-LSH 2022-2025

The SWOT analysis is summarised in Table 4 below.

Table 4: SWOT analysis TDCC-LSH 2022-2025

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>National common platform – Deep connections to key LSH experts and (inter)national initiatives (e.g. LSRI, European LMS-RIs, EHDS), cross-connecting to domain-overarching initiatives (OSNL, LCRDM/LDCCs, SURF, EOSC, NFDI).</p> <p>Recognized and trusted partner with national reach - LSH stakeholders recognize TDCC-LSH network as valid partner in the Dutch LSH domain.</p> <p>Network & events – Strong record in organizing impactful community events and workshops.</p> <p>Strategic project portfolio – Funded first-generation projects well-aligned with the TDCC-LSH Roadmap.</p> <p>Community insight- Deep understanding of needs across broad and niche subdomains.</p> <p>Policy influence – Actively engaged in national policy dialogues, ensuring community needs are represented</p> <p>Governance – Programme Board covers broadness of LSH domain and ensures strategic and balanced project portfolio.</p>	<p>Limited capacity – Small team relative to the size of the community it serves and the high expectations from the community</p> <p>Budget constraints- High demand but limited funding for community projects.</p> <p>Sustainability & scalability challenges - Reliance on temporary funding; no long-term position and funding secured.</p> <p>Relatively late start of project portfolio – given the timeframe from stakeholder consultations in 2021 to start of projects in 2025.</p>

Opportunities	Threats
<p>Alignment & funding – Leverage Open Science NL goals, LSRI roadmap calls, sector plans, and cross-institutional collaboration trends.</p> <p>Regulatory drivers – EHDS and other EU policies push stakeholders to implement data infrastructures, also at a national level.</p> <p>International learning – Adapt and adopt best practices from European initiatives (EOSC, ELIXIR, RDA).</p> <p>NWO Roadmap funding – 2025 top-up call and future Roadmap shaping could support future sustainability and cross-domain innovation.</p> <p>LMS-RIs collaboration – Dutch nodes in European LMS-RIs ready to collaborate, also at the level of common data processes and infrastructure</p>	<p>Sustainability risks– Limited funding available, lack of long-term funding threatens continuity.</p> <p>Long project start-up – Long lead times before visible results may weaken engagement.</p> <p>Stakeholder capacity & timing mismatches – Stakeholder staffing limits reduce ability to join initiatives promptly.</p> <p>Visibility risk – Broker role not always recognised, risking reduced perceived value.</p> <p>Sustainability risk – stakeholders may not be willing to provide ‘own contribution’ to the 2nd phase of the TDCC-LSH <u>network</u> project.</p> <p>Formal administrative hurdle - Health-RI as coordinator of the TDCC-LSH has no further access to NWO funds related to data driven health & life sciences.</p>

3.2 Unique platform enabling knowledge exchange and collaboration

Capitalising on the pre-existing networks of DTL and embedded in the solid organisation and experienced team of Health-RI, the TDCC-LSH team has been able to organise impactful events and well-aligned community-supported projects in line with the three TDCC-LSH ambitions and Roadmap. Through its active network programme, the TDCC-LSH already has become a nationally recognized and trusted partner in the Life Sciences & Health (LSH) domain, valued by stakeholders for its overview, expertise, strategic links and strong community engagement with a broad expert network in data-driven health and life science. The TDCC-LSH programme is expected to stimulate and facilitate the design of interoperable approaches, protocols, guidelines, and (workflow) tools for good data stewardship and FAIR implementation, and subsequent advanced analysis and machine learning/AI approaches (e.g. bioinformatics) in health and life sciences.

The TDCC programme is not meant to deliver scientific results on its own, nor to build research infrastructure, but clearly to enable knowledge transfer within the field and to advance its data driven science practices by facilitating network activities and relatively small-scale collaborative projects that otherwise would be fully reliant on a ‘Friday afternoon commitment’ basis. This role as an enabling network platform connecting stakeholders is seen as a unique strength to build bridges between initiatives, help harmonise research data management and drive capacity building. The concept of the TDCCs, with TDCC-LSH overlooking the broad domain of data driven health and life sciences, is quite unique and stakeholders already mention in this early stage that it needs a long-term position.

The Programme Board and the TDCC-LSH stakeholders broadly confirm the value of this intermediate position, facilitating knowledge transfer from an independent (commons) role. They also value the support provided by NWO as part of its programme to strengthen the digitalisation of research. In this regard, it is highly appreciated that the TDCCs could move away from the regular competition, and that NWO has helped to create a mechanism in which community-led projects could be prioritised by the TDCC-LSH Programme Board based upon their oversight of the (inter)national field.

Stakeholders express their appreciation for the motivated team at Health-RI behind the TDCC-LSH, and for the funding made available by NWO to facilitate unique collaborations. At the same time, there is an inherent mismatch between having a small network coordination team and relatively small TDCC-LSH budget currently available through NWO for the TDCC calls, relative to the size of the field.

Combined with a great need for common interoperable solutions, exemplified by the broad interest in the TDCC-LSH project calls, the Programme Board and several stakeholders recognise a potential risk of a growing mismatch between the expectations from the field, and what TDCC-LSH can offer.

As a first coping strategy to mitigate this risk, and to get the maximum out of this relatively small programme, the Programme Board has taken the active strategy to use the initial phase of the TDCC-LSH programme to engage experienced teams from nationally operating communities and initiatives in the field such as the LSRI's (including Health-RI), BioSB and ELIXIR-NL. As such, the TDCC-LSH programme actively capitalises on these national initiatives, while engaging them in realising the TDCC-LSH ambitions. So far this has paid off, as stakeholders generally appreciate the connections that have been made through TDCC-LSH and they are willing to bring their own capacity to the table to strengthen project activities that also help them move forward in their own initiatives.

3.3 Project portfolio helps realise the TDCC-LSH ambitions

While pursuing this strategy, it has taken more time than originally expected to build the first project portfolio. This has been caused by various factors, on top of exchanging with field initiatives, some issues of administrative nature linked to the novelty of the TDCC-instrument, and delays in hiring experienced personnel. Nevertheless, the Programme Board and the stakeholders are very positive about the current phase of the TDCC-LSH, in which a strong first package of projects has received funding from NWO late 2024, and started in the course of this year. TDCC-LSH has also seized the opportunity to acquire additional funding reserved for the TDCCs as part of the national funds for Open Science. The OSNL programme launched in 2023 offered an opportunity in the course of 2024 to apply for funding to hire dedicated interoperability expertise in the TDCC-LSH team, which was granted by OSNL late 2024 (Project P6 - Interoperability OSNL).

TDCC-LSH meanwhile has facilitated in the interactions among large-scale research infrastructure consortia in the LSH field, where an explicit need was felt for a collective approach to connect the data systems independently developed by several LSRI's.¹ The initiatives have a national infrastructure role for their domain, and recognise the benefit of facilitating scientists to combine the data generated across their experimental set-ups. Several initiatives have arranged a FAIR-by-design workflow at the basis of their research data management systems. The TDCC-LSH Programme Board strongly supports this call for interoperability of data platforms among LSRI's, which is well aligned with one of the three TDCC-LSH core ambitions and fits with the scope of the OSNL-funded TDCC-LSH project (P6). A preparatory small-scale TDCC-LSH project (P9 - LSRI's) will help take the first steps among LSRI teams. The project aims to demonstrate the value of a collective data programme and infrastructure.

Recognising the role of the TDCC-LSH as common platform, several LSRI's have meanwhile also included this angle in the open ['upgrade' grant call that is currently available to them through NWO](#). This may offer immediate opportunities to scale up data interoperability in line with one of the three TDCC-LSH ambitions. Unfortunately, there is a formal hurdle to bring the TDCC-LSH team at Health-RI on board of such proposals as a regular partner, as Health-RI is not eligible to apply for funding through such calls. As this may jeopardise continuity and put the TDCC-LSH behind in its national commons role, Health-RI has opened a dialogue with NWO to improve this situation.

While reporting until September 2025, a next set of community-driven TDCC-LSH projects is expected to be offered to NWO for funding later this year, in the [project call NWO has opened for the TDCCs](#). The Programme Board will review and select full proposals along the criteria set by NWO, how they fit

¹ LSRI's: UNLOCK (microbial fermentation and ~omics data), X-Omics (integration of multi-omics data), NPEC (multiscale genome-phenotyping), NL-Bioimaging-AM (advance light microscopy) and HDMT (organ on a chip measurements). Also, along with other stakeholders, ARISE (biodiversity data) and LTER-LIFE (ecology data) are looking to develop a common data platform for ecosystem research.

the TDCC-LSH Roadmap and prioritise projects that will complement the existing portfolio of activities and initiatives now ongoing in the field. The TDCC-LSH Roadmap deliberately has been set up as a broad framework, giving room to current developments in the field. In an outlook towards expected future calls for projects, the TDCC-LSH Programme Board is planning to take stock of the integral portfolio late 2025, beyond the selection of proposals in the current open round, and determine whether certain communities are to be stimulated to respond in particular. Again, this will be done with an eye on the TDCC-LSH Roadmap and ongoing developments and existing initiatives in the field.

One of the angles may be to look for possibilities to support cross-domain activities between TDCCs, e.g. in the framework of broader societal themes such as public health, and sustainability. It is clear that research here increasingly will require a broad integration of knowledge, data and expertise across domains (science and society, including industry), boosted by the massive availability of data resources (e.g. driven by the European Health Data Space and the transition to Open Science) and next generation machine learning and AI technologies. Such topics may offer new focal points for future TDCC-LSH-supported projects. With its broad network and active working relations as the basis, the Programme Board will determine its future course to make the TDCC-LSH a forward-looking platform recognized and supported by its broad diversity of stakeholders.

3.4 Viability, embedding and outlook towards long-term sustainability

As part of NWO's strategy to strengthen the digitalisation of research in the Dutch academic field, the construct of TDCCs has been foreseen for ten years, divided in two terms of 5 years. As such, the TDCC-LSH is expected to be secured for the upcoming years. However, over this ten-year period, NWO-funding will decline over time, and will have to meet with a growing investment of the field through other channels, building on own contribution of the field. Already, in the current open call for TDCC challenge projects, NWO demands own contribution for TDCC-related projects. Like the other two TDCCs, TDCC-LSH will need to build a strategy to secure its position and access to future NWO funding, also for the network-activities.

In its first phase, the TDCC-LSH team and Programme Board have focussed on establishing the TDCC-LSH basis: a broad collaborative network, a running project portfolio involving a wide range of stakeholders, and a strategic position as common platform for data driven health and life sciences. Now this has been achieved (and will keep growing), it is time to develop a long-term embedding and (diverse!) funding strategy, trying to capitalise on the opportunities that may arise in the moving Dutch (research) data and research infrastructure landscape. TDCC-LSH also looks at the alignment with European policy programmes and related funding schemes in line with the development of (European) research infrastructures and European Data Spaces (including the European Health Data Space and the European Open Science Cloud). Without any of these angles already solidified, we list a number of options we will explore in the coming period to find a future-proof solution for TDCC-LSH, and engage stakeholders in this process.

1. Firstly, the TDCC-LSH will use its embedding in Health-RI and will be taken along in the sustainability strategy of Health-RI itself. Health-RI has its core position in building the national health data infrastructure, in alignment with the national implementation of the European Health Data Space. At the same time, Health-RI bundles the Dutch nodes of European research infrastructures in the biomedical field, such as BBMRI-NL, ELIXIR-NL and EATRIS-NL. As such, it is well positioned to serve the field of data driven health research. The health-related activities of TDCC-LSH fit well with the future role of Health-RI as sustainable national infrastructure supporting the health domain. Health-RI has opened a dialogue with the ministries of VWS (health), OCW (science) and EZ (innovation) and is involving a broad league of stakeholders to

create a sustainable infrastructure in the Netherlands. This may involve a common partnership model, such as used earlier in DTL (2014-2023). While this path may be viable, possibly in combination with the two routes below, we regard it as a potential threat for our TDCC sustainability that NWO has indicated to expect own contribution for the TDCC network coordination in the second phase. We have an experienced team at Health-RI that we want to sustain, and it would not be logic to request Health-RI to provide all requested co-funding. Especially in this time of extensive budget cuts, it is not likely that field parties will provide such own contribution.

2. [Recently, the 15 national nodes of European research infrastructures in the life and medical sciences \(LMS-RIs\) agreed to build a common coordination and support structure](#) and to work together in promoting access to their international-grade resources. They have started to explore how to align their data management systems, possibly designing a common digital infrastructure to connect their facilities and better support their users. This is well aligned with the initiative taken by the LSRI in the life sciences described above, which already has led to first steps supported by TDCC-LSH. As mentioned above, the TDCC role may be taken on board of applications prepared by LSRI collaborating in the NWO LSRI Upgrade call. In the coming period, we will align the work of the TDCC-LSH with both the LSRI and the collaboration initiative of the Dutch nodes in the European LMS-RIs to explore how TDCC-LSH can be taken along in further collective plans.
3. As Health-RI and TDCC-LSH team, we are already well aligned with international initiatives in EOSC from its start, through participation in several taskforces & expert groups (currently: FAIR metrics and Digital Objects; Health Data; Skills, Engagement and Adoption), and European projects in the framework of EOSC-related calls (e.g. cluster projects such as EOSC-Life chaired by ELIXIR, EOSC4Cancer, and recently, EOSC-ENTRUST). In response to the development of the European Open Science Cloud, which is now entering a new phase of solidification through the implementation of the EOSC Federation, the Netherlands is preparing for a clear position to connect relevant services and resources of stakeholders (both research performing and research supporting organisations) and form a Dutch national node in EOSC. Along SURF, DANS and eScience Centre, the TDCCs are directly involved in preparing for this national position in EOSC. For TDCC-LSH it will be important to create synergy with the EHDS, and at the same time, there may be a sustainable role for TDCC-LSH in the national EOSC node organisation. This will be explored with all stakeholders involved, convening in the *Bestuurlijk Overleg Open Science*, with board-level representation of funders NWO, ZonMw and all universities, UMCs, Universities of Applied Science and the research supporting organisations in the Dutch academic field (including the TDCCs). Here, the alignment will also be made to initiatives to realise national infrastructure for Open Science, and with the national [RDNL training and community platform for research data professionals](#) that has [recently received 4M€ of funding from Open Science NL](#). Health-RI is one of the partners in this platform, with a close personal link to the TDCC-LSH team building the national Digital Competence Centre for Life Sciences and Health.

In conclusion, by actively engaging with national stakeholders and funders and exploring multiple embedding and co-funding opportunities with strategic initiatives in the rapidly moving Dutch research data field, we try to secure the sustained position of TDCC-LSH as a national platform connecting stakeholders to enable data driven health and life sciences research in the Netherlands.

Appendix 1: TDCC-LSH Network: Events

This appendix gives an overview of network activities of TDCC-LSH for the period September 2022 – September 2025.

Categories of activities that are listed are:

1. **Community workshops and events**, often co-created with other stakeholders (e.g., the other TDCCs, the LDCCs, LCRDM), to connect initiatives to the TDCC(-LSH) network and provide a platform for discussing challenges and showcasing solutions aligned with the roadmap.
2. **Presentations, webinars, and Q&A sessions** either at national/international events or hosted by TDCC-LSH, aimed at sharing results and encouraging collaboration. Many were held jointly with the other TDCCs.

Note: One-on-one meetings and discussions with specific stakeholders (e.g., challenge call applicants, LSRLs or LDCCs) are not included in this overview.

Stakeholders Involved

Research Performing Organizations (RPOs, IROs)

Research Supporting Organisations (RSOs)

National Infrastructures

International Infrastructures

Data Stewards (e funders)

Policy Drivers (e funders)

TDC-MS&A, TDC-SSH

Name	Date	Location	Role
Outreach (events attended) (38)			
2022			
LORDM networking days (workshop TDC what is in it for me)	01 Nov 2022	Utrecht	Speaker
DTL Scientific Advisory Committee	15 Nov 2022	Utrecht	Speaker
FAIR Data Day	29 Nov 2022	Utrecht	Participant
2023			
FAIR for physical objects workshop	01 Mar 2023	Utrecht	Participant
EOSC-NL Tripartite event	11 Apr 2023	Utrecht	Speaker
WUR WDCC Meetup	20 Apr 2023	Wageningen	Speaker
BioSE Conference 2023	9 - 10 May 2023	Egmond aan Zee	Poster
NWO LIFE 2023	22 - 24 May 2023	Egmond aan Zee	Booth
Open Science Festival 2023	31 Aug 2023	Rotterdam	Booth, Speaker
Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CORDI) 2023	14 Sep 2023	Karlsruhe	Speaker
EOSC Symposium 2023	20 - 22 Sep 2023	Madrid	Speaker
Open Science FAIR	25 - 27 Sep 2023	Madrid	Speaker
Health-RI Conference	12 Oct 2023	Utrecht	Booth
DCC-IN meeting on workflows + career paths data stewards	06 Nov 2023	Utrecht	Moderator
Belux Metabolics Days 2023	16 - 17 Nov 2023	Utrecht	Participant
2024			
NWO - Large Scale Research Infrastructure (LSRI) IT workshop	14 Mar 2024	Utrecht	Participant
X-Omics Festival	15 Apr 2024	Nijmegen	Booth
National Research Software Days (eScience Center)	23 Apr 2024	Hilversum	Participant
NWO LIFE 2024	21 - 23 May 2024	Egmond aan Zee	Booth & Pitch
EOSC-NL Tripartite event	22 May 2024	Utrecht	Speaker
SUIPE Research Days	30 May 2024	Amersfoort	Booth
ELIXIR All Hands meetings	10 Jun 2024	Uppsala	Poster
Belux Metabolics Days 2024	05 Sep 2024	Ghent	Participant
Health-RI Conference	10 Oct 2024	Utrecht	Booth
Open Science Festival 2024	22 Oct 2024	Maastricht	Booth
EOSC Symposium 2024	22 Oct 2024	Berlin	Speaker
Health-RI Knooppuntendag	19 Nov 2024	Nijmegen	Poster
2025			
FAIR coordinators meeting Health-RI	22 Jan 2025	Online	Speaker
International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC)	17 Feb 2025	Den Haag	Poster & Chair
UKB WG Research Data meeting	09 Apr 2025	Online	Speaker
NWO LIFE 2025	28 - 29 May 2025	Egmond aan Zee	Booth
ELIXIR All Hands meeting 2025	02 Jun 2025	Thessaloniki Greece	Poster
LIFES network meeting	10 Jun 2025	Lelidn	Speaker
National RSE onboarding & interoperability day	26 Jun 2025	Utrecht	Speaker
Amsterdam Cohort Hub Conference	01 Jul 2025	Amsterdam	Keynote
Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CORDI) 2025	26 - 28 Aug 2025	Aachen	Speaker & Chair
RDA Workshop Shaping the Future of Data Stewardship	2 - 3 Sep 2025	Ljubljana	Speaker
UMCG Symposium 'FAIR Data, FAIR Future'	18 Sep 2025	Groningen	Speaker

Stakeholders Involved
 Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
 National Infrastructures
 Research Supporting Organisations (RSOs)
 Data awards
 Internal Infrastructures
 Policy Drivers (e.g. funders)
 TDCC-NRES & TDCC-SSH

Name	Date	Location	Role	Stakeholders Involved
DSIG Meetings across domains (12)				
2022	27 Sep 2022	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
2023	12 Jan 2023	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	16 Feb 2023	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	23 Mar 2023	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	19 Apr 2023	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	16 May 2023	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
2024	01 Feb 2024	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	02 Jul 2024	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	14 Oct 2024	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	26 Nov 2024	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
2025	26 May 2025	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	11 Sep 2025	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
TDCC-LSH Project Information sessions (7)				
2023	19 Dec 2023	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	20 Dec 2023	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
2024	16 Jan 2024	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	13 Mar 2023	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	14 Mar 2023	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
2025	31 Mar 2025	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
	10 Sep 2025	Online	Organizer	Research performing Organizations (RPOs) / FPOs
Total				55 31 28 21 57 15 27

Appendix 2: TDCC-LSH Project portfolio

Appendix 2A. Describes the TDCC-LSH Challenge project selection process.

Appendix 2B. Provides an overview of the numbering and submitted proposal titles in the TDCC-LSH Challenge project process.

Appendix 2C. Provides an overview of the submitted proposals in the TDCC-LSH Challenge project process along with a visual representation of the participating institutions.

Appendix 2D. Offers a detailed description of the TDCC-LSH project portfolio including project title, keywords, project lead, budget, duration, start date, responsible institutions and public summaries.

2A. TDCC-LSH Challenge project selection process

The 2023–2024 selection process followed a structured five-step approach aimed at refining project ideas and fostering meaningful collaboration. It began with the submission of an Expression of Interest (EOI), during which the TDCC-LSH team conducted an initial eligibility check and provided applicants with suggestions or potential collaborators to promote synergy across proposals. Selected applicants were invited to develop pre-proposals, allowing them to further refine their project ideas and strengthen proposed collaborations. In the second phase, the TDCC-LSH Programme Board reviewed the pre-proposals, offering constructive feedback on proposal quality, relevance to community needs and potential partnerships. This iterative feedback process helped applicants refine their concepts even further before progressing to the development of full Proposals using the NWO's ISAAC application format. In the third phase, these comprehensive full proposals underwent final evaluation by the TDCC-LSH Programme Board. Upon approval, TDCC-LSH issued official letters of support, which were an essential requirement for submitting proposals to the NWO call and marked the fourth and fifth steps of the process. Throughout this multi-step process, TDCC-LSH played an active role in supporting applicants through Q&A sessions, detailed feedback and facilitating connections across initiatives to increase collaborative opportunities and maximize potential impact.

In 2025, TDCC-LSH revised the process in response to feedback from participants, who found the previous structure to be time-consuming and administratively demanding. The pre-proposal stage was removed to streamline the workflow and reduce the administrative burden while preserving the quality of feedback and proposal development. Instead, the Expression of Interest (EOI) phase was expanded to include key elements previously covered in the pre-proposal phase, making it more detailed and strategically focused. This enabled the TDCC-LSH Programme Board and TDCC-LSH team to provide more comprehensive feedback and evaluation early on in the process. Following feedback on their EOI submissions, applicants were invited to proceed directly to the Full Proposal stage and follow the same process as in 2023–2024.

TDCC-LSH Challenge project process 2023/2024

2B. TDCC-LSH Challenge project application overview: numbering and titles of submitted proposals

Proposal Titles submitted 2023-2024:	
#	
1	genAI for training & support in digital LSH research
2	Scaling BASELINE implementation across DCCs
3	Patient Centered Anticoagulation Data Research
4	FAIR Expert Team
5	Towards a common data space in biodiversity research
P3	6 A FAIR tool framework for bioinformatics services, tools and workflows in digital Life Sciences and Health (LSH) research
P4	7 LEARN-FAIR: Life Science & Health Educational Alignment for Research and Networking in FAIR Data Management
8	Cohort and mentorship training in open skills for the LSH domain
9	Let Galaxy connects researchers, bioinformaticians, and students
P5	10 Training the next generation of FAIR-aware and AI-savvy data scientists for the LSH domain
11	Federated Learning for Enhanced Privacy-Preserving Image Analysis
12	Multimodal Monitoring of the Respiratory Pump: an integrated analysis platform (M3RESP)
13	Interoperable Data Management Plans (iDMPs)
14	A community-driven Python library for better importing of data into Castor EDC
15	FAME: FAIR Metadata Exchange
16	Health-MetaSyn: FAIR and safe synthetic data from health record meta-data
17	Empowering 'Citizen Science for Health' patient communities with open science methods and tools.
18	Expanding the Grand Challenge Horizon Beyond Imaging: Toward Trustworthy Multicenter Benchmarking in Genomics
P8	19 Prospective harmonization of variables through Common Data Elements – towards a core cohort dataset for cohort studies in the Netherlands
20	Brain and neurocognitive development in sickle cell disease (BRICK-study)
P7	21 FAIRify your metabolomics data: achieving convergence on standards for reuse-ready data and workflows (FAIRify)
22	TREAT: veTeRinary patiEnt dATa
Proposal Titles submitted 2025	
23	A data portal to share
24	FUNGI (FAIR, Users, Networks, Genomics, Infrastructure)-NL: A National Hub for FAIR Fungal Research in the Netherlands
25	Decision Support in Data Access Requests
26	A Standardized Software Management Plan for UMCs in the Netherlands
27	Guidelines and Training in data reuse in non-clinical healthcare research utilising Machine Learning and AI
28	RegOmics – Enabling Ontology-Driven, Interoperable & Accessible Omics for Regulatory Science
29	How AI tools can help making our research software FAIR – increasing Reusability and Interoperability
30	A Dutch community for sharing and using knowledge with SPARQL
31	OPEN-MRH: A FAIR Infrastructure and Data Standard for Medication-Related Harm Research
32	Strategic roadmap for a Dutch TEF-Health

2D. TDCC-LSH Project portfolio

TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Bottleneck project #P2
Project Status: TDCC-LSH Programme board & NWO approved in 2025

Title: Strengthening the Dutch LSH FAIR data stewardship landscape – installing a national cohort of FAIR LSH fellows

Key words: Fellowship, Large Scale Research Infrastructures, Domain specific data stewards, National network of experts, Training, Capacity Building, FAIR.

Project lead: Dr. C.W.G. (Celia) van Gelder

Duration: 18 months ; start date April 1, 2025

Budget: € 877.776

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Systems and Synthetic Biology & UNLOCK
- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Genetics & NPEC
- Naturalis, ARISE
- Leiden University (LU), LIACS & NEMI & NL-Bioimaging
- UMC Groningen (UMCG), Faculty of Medical Sciences & NEMI & NL-Bioimaging
- UMC Groningen (UMCG), Genetics, Genomics Coordination Center & X-Omics
- Amsterdam UMC (AUMC), Medical Informatics
- GO FAIR Foundation (GFF)
- Health-RI

Public Summary:

Digital research data is increasingly important for research in the life sciences and the health domain. This programme aims to increase the knowledge needed to carefully manage this data and, if possible, make it usable for follow-up research. Research institutions in the Netherlands can delegate a fellow. The TDCC-LSH fellows receive training and work for a year under the guidance of a coach on their digital skills and on joint solutions. This creates a national network of experts that ensures that knowledge is shared and can be applied by all research organizations in this domain.

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TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Bottleneck project #P9
Project Status: Submitted to NWO on June 26, 2025

Title: Towards Practical FAIR Metadata Use in Life Science Research Infrastructures

Key words: FAIR, Meta datamanagement, Large Scale Research Infrastructures, FAIR by Design, Interoperability

Project lead: dr. J.J. (Jasper) Koehorst (WUR)

Duration: 12 months ; start date T.B.D.

Budget: € 70.651

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Laboratory of Systems and Synthetic Biology
- NL-Bioimaging (Nodes: Amsterdam UMC, UMC Groningen, University of Leiden, LUMC, University of Maastricht)
- NEMI (Nodes: UMC Groningen, University of Maastricht)
- UNLOCK (Nodes: Wageningen University & Research, Delft University of Technology)
- hDMT-INFRA-StemCells (Nodes: UMC Utrecht, Leiden UMC)
- X-OMICS (Nodes: Radboud UMC)

Public Summary:

Domain-specific Research infrastructures develop tailored data and metadata management systems to address their individual challenges. While vital for sharing domain-specific data globally, these systems often create silos that cannot be easily integrated with other diverse data types. At an institutional level, generic solutions like iRODS/Yoda offer secure data management and storage but struggle with integration between data types due to limitations with metadata management, hindering FAIR compliance. This project aims to explore the landscape, from generic to specific, and to identify solutions that will address the challenge of cross domain integration.

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TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Challenge project #P3
Project Status: TDCC-LSH Programme board & NWO approved in 2023/2024 call

Title: A FAIR tool framework for bioinformatics services, tools and workflows in digital Life Sciences and Health (LSH) research

Key words: Tools and software, FAIR, research data management, communities, training

Project lead: Dr. H. (Halima) Mouhib

Duration: 24 months ; start date April 1, 2025

Budget: € 394.325

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Maastricht University (UM), Department of Bioinformatics - BiGCaT
- Prinses Máxima Centrum voor Kinderoncologie (PMC), Research Department
- Leiden University Medical Centre (LUMC), Department of Human Genetics
- Leiden University Medical Centre (LUMC), Center for Proteomics and Metabolomics
- University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG), Department of Genetics
- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU), Department of Computer Science
- Amsterdam UMC (AUMC), Department of Research Data Management
- Netherlands eScience Center (NLLeSC)
- SURF, Research Development
- Health-RI
- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Bioinformatics Department
- Radboudumc, Department of Medical BioSciences

Public Summary:

Various tools and services are available for Life Science and Health data research, but users cannot easily find them or assess their quality. As a result, they are not used, or even similar tools are redeveloped. Together with developers, experts and users, we develop a toolkit for finding suitable tools and services. This is applied to existing tools and those under development and can be used with new tools in the future. With examples, training, interactive work sessions and collaboration with established platforms and communities, tools and services become sustainably accessible to end users and (further) development cycles for developers.

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TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Challenge project #P4
Project Status: TDCC-LSH Programme board & NWO approved in 2023/2024 call

Title: LEARN-FAIR: Life Science & Health Educational Alignment for Research and Networking in FAIR Data Management

Key words: FAIR Data Stewardship, Community Building, Open Educational Resources

Project lead: Dr. M.G. (Martijn) Kersloot

Duration: 24 months ; start date April 1, 2025

Budget: € 399.857

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Amsterdam UMC (AUMC), Medical Informatics
- Health-RI
- Leiden University Medical Centre (LUMC), Department of Human Genetics
- Maastricht University (UM), DataHub
- Radboud UMC (RUMC), Department of Medical BioSciences

Public Summary:

The LEARN-FAIR project intends to foster cooperation and knowledge exchange among FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data) trainers by establishing a Dutch FAIR Trainers Community. Additionally, the project focuses on identifying training needs for researchers and data stewards, as well as existing educational materials, in order to develop new Open Educational Resources. To ensure that these materials meet the (future) needs of the community, the LEARN-FAIR project combines empirical research with active community engagement.

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TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Challenge project #P5
Project Status: TDCC-LSH Programme board & NWO approved in 2023/2024 call

Title: Training the next generation of FAIR-aware and AI-savvy data scientists for the LSH domain

Key words: Education, data stewardship, FAIR workflows, artificial intelligence, bioinformatics and systems biology

Project lead: Dr. ir. P. (Perry) Moerland

Duration: 24 months ; start date June 1, 2025

Budget: € 243.158

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Amsterdam UMC (AUMC), Epidemiology and Data Science
- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Bioinformatics
- Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e), Biomedical engineering
- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU), Computer science
- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Systems and Synthetic Biology "

Public Summary:

For professionals in life sciences and health (LSH), it's increasingly crucial to (i) efficiently link findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data with computational workflows that process the data (FAIR workflows); (ii) ensure that the data produced by FAIR workflows can be seamlessly utilized for artificial intelligence (AI) applications (AI-ready); (iii) construct AI models while integrating pertinent domain-specific knowledge (AI-savvy). The objective of this project is to create two new post-Master's courses on FAIR workflows and advanced machine learning/modern AI technology for life sciences. These courses aim to address the existing gap in equipping researchers with these essential skills.

TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Challenge project #P7
Project Status: TDCC-LSH Programme board & NWO approved in 2023/2024 call

Title: FAIRify your metabolomics data: achieving convergence on standards for reuse-ready data and workflows (FAIRify)

Key words: Metabolomics, FAIR Data, FAIR Workflows, Data Stewardship Practices, Data Stewardship Training

Project lead: Prof. dr. T. (Thomas) Hankemeier

Duration: 24 months ; start date August 1, 2025

Budget: € 329.930

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Leiden University (LU), Leiden Academic Centre for Drug Research (LACDR) department, MAC, Faculty of Science Data Steward
- Maastricht University (UM), BiGCaT/NUTRIM
- Wageningen University & Research (WUR), Plant Sciences & Bioinformatics department
- Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU), Chemistry and Pharmaceutical Sciences department
- Radboud University Medical Center (RUMC), TML, Department of Human Genetics
- Utrecht University (UU), Faculty of Veterinary Medicine department
- Amsterdam University Medical Center (AUMC), Genetic Metabolic Diseases department
- University of Groningen (RUG), Groningen Research Institute of Pharmacy
- Health RI / Netherlands Metabolomics Centre (Health RI / NMC), Life Sciences & Metabolomics
- TNO, Digital Health Innovations
- GO FAIR Foundation

Public Summary:

Metabolomics is a data-rich field undergoing rapid growth. The FAIR principles provide guidance on how to make data Findable, Accessible, automatically Interoperable, and maximally Reusable. Scalable solutions for making metabolomics data FAIR can only be built on broadly accepted agreements on FAIR standards. In project FAIRify, the Netherlands Metabolomics Community will work together to develop processes for catalysing convergence onto FAIR standards for metabolomics. This process will be used to FAIRify high-priority data and will itself be reusable in other omics fields and after the project ends. FAIRify kick-starts a culture of FAIR data creation and stewardship for metabolomics research.

TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Challenge project #P8
Project Status: TDCC-LSH Programme board & NWO approved in 2023/2024 call

Title: Prospective harmonization of variables through Common Data Elements – towards a core cohort dataset for cohort studies in the Netherlands

Key words: Prospective harmonisation, Common Data Elements, longitudinal cohort study, core data set, FAIR data

Project lead: Dr. K.J. (Joeri) van der Velde

Duration: 24 months ; start date September 1, 2025

Budget: € 231.760

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG); Cohort and Biobank Coordination Hub (CBCH) and Genomics Coordination Center (GCC) department
- Amsterdam University Medical Center (AUMC), Department of Public and Occupational Health (DPOH), Department of Medical Informatics (KIK), Department of Research Data Management (RDM)
- University Medical Center Utrecht (UMCU), Julius Center for Health Sciences and Primary Care (JC) department
- Erasmus Medical Center (EMC), department Epidemiology (EPI), Netherlands Cohorts Consortium (NCC)
- Maastricht University Medical Center + (MUMC+); DataHub, Medische Informatie Technology (MIT); Klinische Epidemiologie en Medische Technology Assessment (KEMTA) department
- Health-RI, FAIR Data department

Public Summary:

Dutch long-term cohort studies monitor the health of large groups of people. They collect data differently, making combining data and doing research together difficult. This project aims make data from Dutch long-term cohort studies more comparable. We will identify core study data, harmonize with existing best practices and add it to a national standard. This makes it easier for data from new cohorts to be used together for research. We also test whether our standard can be used for existing cohort studies and for specific disease areas, such as depression and diabetes. This project contributes to better data for research.

TDCC-LSH project reference ID: TDCC-LSH Interoperability #P6
Project Status: TDCC-LSH Programme board & OSNL approved in 2025

Title: Collective research data workflow assembly to enhance FAIR practices across the Dutch Life Sciences and Health domain

Key words: Interoperability, Metadata, Technical, Semantic, Tools & Resources, Community

Project lead: K.C. (Kimberley) Zwiers

Duration: 44 months ; start date June 1, 2025

Budget: € 998.128

Responsible institution(s) and department(s):

- Health-RI

Public Summary:

Researchers within the Life Sciences and Health domain have a hard time to find, access and reuse data resources relevant to them. This project will help improve this situation and boost the transition to Open Science by making data resources more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) across the Dutch LSH domain, while collaborating with existing initiatives. International alignment comes from close involvement in organisations such as ELIXIR, EOOSC and RDA. We will appoint a FAIR metadata specialist and a bioinformatics/technical specialist to support alignment among LSH research initiatives and help realise a collective FAIR data environment valuable for end-users.

Appendix 3: Finances TDCC-LSH

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Appendix 4: Stakeholder Consultations 2025

Stakeholder Group	Representing	Name	Date
RPOs	LDCC -UMC	Efi Gkoumassi (UMCG)	01-09-2025
RPOs	LDCC -UMC	Maria Vivas Romero (MUMC+)	01-09-2025
RPOs	LDCC - Univ	Marcel Ras (VU)	03-09-2025
RPOs	LDCC - Univ	Samantha Larson (VU)	03-09-2025
RPOs	Research communities - BioSB	Patrick Kemmeren (PMC)	05-09-2025
RSOs	SURF	Laurents Sesink (SURF)	02-09-2025
RSOs	SURF	Peter Hinrich (SURF)	02-09-2025
National infrastructures	LSRI - Health	Peter-Bram 't Hoen (Radboudumc, X-omics/Health-RI)	14-08-2025
National infrastructures	LSRI - LS	Sharif Islam (Naturalis, ARISE)	01-09-2025
National infrastructures	LSRI - LS	Geerten Hengeveld (NIOO-KNAW, ELTER-LIFE)	01-09-2025
International infrastructures	ELIXIR-NL	Magnus Palmblad (LUMC)	05-09-2025
International infrastructures	EOSC	Karel Luyben	27-08-2025
Data stewards	DSIG	Anna Niehues (LUMC)	01-09-2025
Data stewards	DSIG	Kristina Hettne (LU)	01-09-2025
Policy drivers	Funder	Ellen Carbo (ZonMW)	04-09-2025

Appendix 5: TDCC-LSH Governance

TDCC-LSH Programme Board

The Programme Board is composed of members that represent major communities in the broad data driven Health and Life Sciences research domain. Since the end of 2023 the TDCC-LSH Programme Board meets 3-4 times per year to review progress in the TDCC-LSH programme and guides the TDCC coordination team in its work with research communities in the LSH domain. NWO and ZonMw are observers of these Programme Board meetings. The TDCC-LSH Programme Board is also in charge of selecting community-driven projects that will be set up under the TDCC-LSH umbrella with funding support from NWO or other funders.

Composition of the TDCC-LSH Programme Board

- Representatives of each of the four groups of the Roadmap Large Scale Research infrastructures (LSRI):
 - LSRI-Group Health Sciences
 - LSRI-Group Medical Sciences
 - LSRI-Group Green Life Sciences
 - LSRI-Group Life Sciences & Enabling Technologies
- Representatives from key national initiatives in data driven health & life sciences:
 - BioSB (Bioinformatics and Systems Biology research and education)
 - ELIXIR-NL (national node of the European ELIXIR infrastructure for life sciences data)
 - Health-RI (establishing the national health data infrastructure for research and innovation).
- Co-leads of the TDCC-LSH field consultation and Roadmap design appointed by NWO.
- Chair

TDCC-LSH Programme Board members (per August 2024):

- Prof. dr. Nine Knoers (Professor of Genetics, UMC Groningen, on behalf of LSRI - Health Sciences Group)
- Dr. ir. Koen Vincken (Associate Professor of Image Sciences Institute (ISI), UMC Utrecht, on behalf of LSRI - Medical Sciences Group)
- Prof. dr. Alain van Gool (Professor of Personalized Healthcare, Radboudumc, on behalf of LSRI - LSET Group)
- Prof. dr. Hauke Smidt (Professor of Molecular Ecology, Wageningen University, on behalf of LSRI - Green Life Sciences group)
- Prof. dr. Sanne Abeln (Professor of AI Technology for Life, Utrecht University, on behalf of BioSB)
- Prof. dr. Jaap Heringa (Professor of Bioinformatics, VU-university Amsterdam, on behalf of ELIXIR-NL)
- Prof. dr. Gerrit Meijer (Professor of Pathology, the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI), CSO and Board member at Health-RI).
- Dr. Ruben Kok (CSA and Board member at Health-RI, co-lead TDCC-LSH Roadmap, chair of the TDCC-LSH Programme Board)
- Prof. Dr. Vera van Noort (Professor of Computational Biology, Leiden University and Leuven University, co-lead TDCC-LSH Roadmap)

TDCC-LSH team

Financially supported by NWO to help strengthen digital research, a small team positioned at host organization Health-RI acts as the TDCC-LSH network coordination team. The TDCC-LSH coordination team informs all relevant stakeholders in the TDCC-LSH network and coordinates the TDCC-LSH programme. The TDCC-LSH coordination team also facilitates the community-driven project call process and guides or monitors the progress of TDCC-LSH projects and their selected project teams.

- Network manager: Dr. Celia van Gelder
- Community Coordinator Life Sciences: Kimberley Zwiers, MSc
- Community Coordinator Health: Dr. Fieke Schoots
- Community Manager BioSB: Petra Aarnoutse, BSc
- Community Manager: Dr. Meike Bungler
- Project coordinator Fellowship Project: Dr. Carla Strubbia (starting 1 September 2025)
- FAIR data stewardship lead: Dr. Mijke Jetten
- Interoperability expert: Dr. Walter Baccinelli (started 1 July 2025)
- Interoperability expert: Dr. Vedran Kasalica (starting 15 September 2025)
- TDCC-LSH Roadmap author & Programme Board chair: Dr. Ruben Kok

Appendix 6: List of abbreviations

BBMRI-NL	European biobanking research infrastructure, Dutch Node
BioSB	Netherlands Bioinformatics and Systems Biology Community
Bottleneck projects	Bottleneck projects are projects funded by a one-off investment of €950,000 by NWO, aimed at addressing key challenges as outlined in the TDCC-LSH Roadmap
Challenge projects	Challenge projects are mid-sized projects (24 months, €50,000–€400,000) that are selected through a transparent or community-driven TDCC-LSH process and are funded via an annual NWO call.
Committee DO	NWO Digitalisation Research Advisory Committee (Digitalisering Onderzoek in Dutch: DO)
CoRDI	Conference on Research Data Infrastructure of NFDI, Germany
DCC-IN	Digital Competence Centre Implementation Network
DSIG	Data Steward Interest Group
DTL	Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences
EATRIS-NL	European infrastructure for translational medicine, Dutch Node
EHDS	European Health Data Space
ELIXIR-NL	European infrastructure for health & life sciences data, Dutch Node
EoI	Expression of Interest
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
Health-RI	Health Research Infrastructure
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCRDM	National Coordination Point Research Data Management
LDCC	Local Digital Competence Centre
LMS-RI	Life and Medical Sciences Research Infrastructure
LSH	Life Sciences and Health
LSRI	Large Scale Research Infrastructure (in Dutch: Grootchalige wetenschappelijke infrastructuur (GWI))
NGF	National Growth Fund
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (Germany)
OSNL	Open Science NL
PC-GWI	Permanent Committee for large-scale scientific infrastructure
PB	TDCC-LSH Programme Board
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDNL	Research Data Netherlands
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations
RSOs	Research Supporting Organisations
SURF	Coöperatie SURF (Samenwerkende Universitaire Reken Faciliteiten)
TDCC	Thematic Digital Competence Centre
TDCC-LSH	Thematic Digital Competence Centre for Life Sciences and Health
TDCC-NES	Thematic Digital Competence Centre for the Natural & Engineering Sciences
TDCC-SSH	Thematic Digital Competence Centre for Social Sciences & Humanities
ToR	Terms of Reference
UMC	University Medical Centre